

MASTER'S THESIS 2021

Technology-driven Startup Processes

Venture Development of Videm and Compular
at Chalmers School of Entrepreneurship

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Executive Summary

This master's thesis is created within the Chalmers Master's program Entrepreneurship and Business Design. During the last year of the Master's program, the authors have been in the drivers' seats of high technology ventures within the fields of molecular simulations and point-of-care in vitro diagnostics.

Included in this thesis are the main Independent study together with six appended competence development studies. The Independent study is conducted to investigate and research an area related to entrepreneurship and the venture creation process. The competence development studies have been developed in order to provide valuable guidance in the venture creation process as well as enabling academic learning.

Independent Study (IND)

This study aims to explore what processes early stage technology-driven startups follow and/or recommend. Following an inductive process based on empirical data collection from 16 tech-driven ventures, qualitative insights could be established answering three main research questions. The study indicates that lean startup principles are mostly coherent to the processes used and recommended by tech-driven entrepreneurs. However, those principles are not suggested to be used "as is", but rather as cognitive rationale guiding specific implementations depending on the ventures' contexts. The authors encourage further exploration within the field of technology-driven entrepreneurial processes to provide more insights than the scope of this thesis allows.

Entrepreneurial Mindset and Teamwork (EMT)

Friendship in Entrepreneurial Teams (Petter Barreng)

This study is a reflective exploration of the author's first year of starting a venture together with a team. Personal experiences are linked to theory regarding friendship and its effects on entrepreneurial team work. The study also reaches conclusions with regards to how friendship in teams can be improved.

Navigating a New Venture through Uncertainty (Emil Krutmeijer)

Through an overview of existing literature and analytical reflection of personal accounts linked to entrepreneurship; the study evaluates why entrepreneurship and uncertainty go hand in hand with creating value. Main discussion points include entrepreneurs' perspective, motivation and processes relating to a future that is uncertain.

Technology and Product Development (TPD)

Market Entry Strategy (Videm)

A study that dives into the topic of what market a point-of-care in vitro diagnostics company should enter first. A thorough evaluation was performed, comparing benefits and disadvantages with regards to market entry in a low and middle income setting or in a high income setting in the ventures home country. The study also explored how to enter the chosen market.

Evaluation of Target Market Segment (Compular)

The purpose of the study was to discuss and reason for the most suitable target segment matching the company's technological capabilities and prerequisites. Based on a theoretical framework including Techno-Economic Analysis and Market Development Strategy Checklist; empirical findings from 33 interviews in potential market segments were analysed and discussed.

Entrepreneurial Strategy, Sales and Execution (ESSE)

Sales in Medical Device Diagnostics (Videm)

The aim of this study was to understand how sales are performed in the medical device diagnostics market today. In addition, predictions of future trends were taken into consideration. Two experts in the field were interviewed contributing to valuable insights and points for discussion.

Sales of B2B-Software for R&D Purposes (Compular)

With the purpose of investigating how sales is performed in the B2B software industry, the study included; a brief literature review of B2B sales; interviews with two larger analytical software companies; and a discussion linking empirical findings to established academic and industry literature with regards to sales process initiation, buyer's journey, stakeholder management, and co-creation of value.

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Abstract

In the past few years, practitioner-grounded methods have been increasingly adopted by market-driven ventures. However, few scholars have attempted to explore the processes applicable to technology-driven entrepreneurship. Especially with regards to the suitability of processes enacting lean startup principles in those types of settings. Thus, this study aims to advance the current understanding of technology-driven entrepreneurial processes. By following an inductive approach, data from 16 semi-structured interviews allowed for a qualitative review of findings, in accordance with the proposed research purpose.

Although technology-driven entrepreneurs by definition initialise their entrepreneurial journeys based on R&D results, our findings suggest that market demands lie at the core of their early-stage venture processes. Except for medtech-based ventures, technology-driven ventures mostly concentrate on unforeseen opportunities in favour of existing technologies. Relating to the theory of effectuation, this seems to suggest that technology-driven entrepreneurs mostly follow effectual processes by leveraging contingencies instead of assuming pre-determined ends. Furthermore, a main contribution in this study relates to the fact that technology-driven entrepreneurs seem to use logic models (abstract thought based guidance) to a higher extent than tools (concrete action-based techniques).

In summary, this study indicates that lean startup principles are mostly coherent to the processes used and recommended by tech-driven entrepreneurs. However, those principles are not suggested to be used “as is”, but rather as cognitive rationale guiding specific implementations depending on the ventures’ contexts. The authors encourage further exploration within the field of technology-driven entrepreneurial processes to provide more insights than the scope of this thesis allows.

Keywords: Technology-driven entrepreneurship, Early-stage startup process, The Lean Startup

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Finally we would like to thank our families for supporting us in the pursuit of a long and challenging academic career which has (most likely) now come to an end.

Happy reading,

Petter and Emil

List of abbreviations

- CSE: Chalmers School of Entrepreneurship
- CV: Chalmers Ventures
- LEAD: LiU Entrepreneurship And Development – Business incubator
- LOI: Letter Of Intent
- MDE: Market-driven Entrepreneurship
- MVP: Minimal Viable Product
- PMF: Product-market fit
- R&D: Research and Development
- RQ: Research Question
- TDE: Technology-driven Entrepreneurship
- VP: Vice President

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1

Introduction

In recent years, approaches following guidelines described in the lean startup methodology (Ries, 2011; Blank and Dorf, 2012) have been increasingly adopted by accelerators (Christiansen, 2009; Mansoori, Karlsson and Lundqvist, 2019) and market-driven ventures (Wirtz, Schilke and Ullrich, 2010; Bortolini *et al.*, 2018). Those approaches focus on iterative learning from potential customers in favour of conventional business planning approaches. The academic literature examining the lean startup approach has matured in the past years. Scholars have attempted to study its advantages and disadvantages (York and Danes, 2014; Silva *et al.*, 2020), proposing opportunities to reduce the academic-practitioner divide (Shepherd and Gruber, 2020), and studying the entrepreneurial cognitions behind the methodology (Ladd and Kendall, 2017; Mansoori and Lackeus, 2019; Yang, Sun and Zhao, 2019). Still, a gap in current research can be identified with regards to if those processes are applicable in the context of technology-driven entrepreneurship. In a systematic review and research agenda of agile methodologies for business model innovation (Silva *et al.*, 2020), the authors pose several research questions relevant for further research. Those include “Are the frameworks/models suitable to all industries?” and “Is Lean Startup applicable to technology-based ventures beyond software?” (Silva *et al.*, 2020, p. 614). Shepherd and Gruber raise similar inquiries in a recent study (Shepherd and Gruber, 2020, p. 18), questioning the usefulness of the lean startup approach in deep technology settings due to the substantial upfront investments to arrive at an MVP. Thus, this study intends to contribute to fill this research gap. By conducting semi-structured interviews with 16 technology-driven entrepreneurs, findings with regards to what entrepreneurial processes are used and/or recommended in the early stages of venture development are discussed and general conclusions of the applicability of lean startup principles for technology-driven ventures are brought forward.

1.1. Research purpose

The purpose of this thesis is to study the processes early stage technology-driven startups follow and/or recommend in early startup stages. In a wider perspective, the authors aim to explore the similarities between processes recommended by early-stage entrepreneurs and lean startup principles.

The thesis should distinctively answer these research questions:

1. To what extent do technology-driven startups *follow* different early-stage venture processes.
2. To what extent do technology-driven startups *recommend* different early-stage venture processes.
3. What entrepreneurial *models* are used by technology-driven startups in early venture development stages.

1.2. Background

We, as authors, have personal experience of market-driven entrepreneurship (MDE) through our own entrepreneurial endeavours by mentoring nascent entrepreneurs and by studying action based courses at University of New South Wales, Linköping University and Chalmers University of Technology. Correspondingly, we have hands-on experience of technology-driven entrepreneurship (TDE) through LEAD Business Incubator, the startup Glana Sensors and learnings from Chalmers School of Entrepreneurship (CSE). More importantly, as part of our second year master studies at CSE (Track: Technology Venture Creation), we are running technology-driven startups in the fields of molecular simulations and in vitro diagnostics respectively.

1.3. Key terminology

Technology-driven entrepreneurship

Technology-driven entrepreneurship occurs where R&D experimentation and scientific breakthroughs precede market opportunity analysis and the development of a business model. (Habtay, 2012)

Market-driven entrepreneurship

Market-driven entrepreneurship begins with the consumer creating demand pressure, thus market opportunities precedes a firm's likely investment in R&D. (Souder, 1989; Habtay, 2012)

Entrepreneurial models

A set of non-mutually exclusive methods, prescriptions, tactics and frameworks established in both academic and non-academic literature.

Medical technology (Medtech)

“Medical technology can be defined as the application of science to develop solutions to health problems or issues such as the prevention or delay of onset of diseases or the promotion and monitoring of good health.” (Tulchinsky and Varavikova, 2014)

Entrepreneurial processes

Functions, activities and actions associated with perceiving opportunities and creating organizations to pursue them. (Bygrave, 2004)

Market pull

Current solutions are of inadequate satisfaction of customer needs, which results in new demands for problem-solving. The impulse comes from individuals or groups who articulate their subjective demands. (Brem and Voigt, 2009)

2

Theory

As a basis for the proposed methodology and discussion of findings, this chapter includes descriptions of technology-driven versus market-driven entrepreneurship and how those views can be linked to Schumpeterian versus Kirznerian views of entrepreneurship; a theoretical overview of early venture development stages; and an overview of commonly prescribed entrepreneurial processes.

2.1. Entrepreneurship theory

Even though the concept around “entrepreneurship” can be traced back to the early 1700s by the writings of Richard Cantillon (Hébert and Link, 1988) – and further developed by a host of writers such as Jean-Baptiste Say and Adam Smith (Bull and Willard, 1993; McDaniel, 2005) – many contemporary theories of entrepreneurship build upon contributions by Joseph Schumpeter in the early 1900s (Hébert and Link, 1988; Gartner, 1990; Bull and Willard, 1993; Braunerhjelm, 2008). By introducing the notion of ‘creative destruction’, Schumpeter emphasised the role of entrepreneurs in converting new knowledge and new technology into business opportunities, thereby creating entirely new industries which over time become the basis for a nation’s wealth generation (Schumpeter, 1911/1934).

Rejecting Schumpeter’s view, Israel Kirzner (1973) argued that entrepreneurship is more of a demand-driven process. Entrepreneurs have a motive of exploiting market opportunities and reacting to – rather than forcing changes in – output mix and consumer tastes. “Alert entrepreneurs are attracted to notice suboptimalities because they respond to the scent of pure profit which accompanies such suboptimalities” (Kirzner, 1992, p. 173). Contemporary research indicates that Schumpeterian and Kirznerian perspectives are equally valid (Ripsas, 1998; Shane,

2003; McMullen, Plummer and Acs, 2007; De Jong and Marsili, 2010; Sundqvist *et al.*, 2012). The differences mainly depend on the contexts such as degree of market saturation, organisational characteristics and existing knowledge as well as entrepreneurial alignment such as opportunity discovery, innovativeness and equilibration.

While the Schumpeterian view regard the entrepreneur to be an innovator who disturbs the economic equilibrium by initiating technological change (Schumpeter, 1911/1934), the Kirznerian view implies that entrepreneurs profits on the quicker adaptation of responding to imperfections or changes in the market (Kirzner, 1973). The differentiation between the two concepts can be expressed through the distinction between technology-driven and market-driven entrepreneurship (Habtay, 2012).

Furthermore, there exists considerable disagreement between scholars as to the nature of entrepreneurship as an academic discipline (Moroz and Hindle, 2012). Some authors put emphasis on exploratory theory building while others argue for an applied management field with cross-fertilization from related domains such as strategic management (Whitley, 1984; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000; Zahra and Dess, 2001; Katz, 2003). Thus, several scholars suggest a process-focused approach for understanding and balancing pure theory development with practice-based theorising. (Low and MacMillan, 1988; Ucbasaran, Westhead and Wright, 2001; Bygrave, 2006; Zahra, 2007). To guide the methodology of this study, an adaptation of Bygrave's (2004) definition of entrepreneurial processes is used: "functions, activities and actions associated with perceiving opportunities and creating organizations to pursue them".

2.2. Technology-driven entrepreneurship

Even though the definitions and/or terms easily get intertwined and used differently depending on the context, *technology-driven entrepreneurship (TDE)* is in most cases synonymous to *technology-push* or *technology entrepreneurship*. Based on a review of 93 articles, Bailetti (2012) finds that "technology entrepreneurship is about: i) operating small businesses owned by engineers or scientists; ii) finding problems or applications for a particular technology; iii) launching new ventures, introducing new applications, or exploiting opportunities that rely on

scientific and technical knowledge; and iv) working with others to produce technology change.” For example, Venkataraman and Sarasvathy (2001) describe TDE as “solutions in search of problems”, which points towards a more discovery-based definition, while Byers et al. (2011) define it as the “creation of new business firms for exploiting the technological innovations”, leaning towards a more creative-based definition. Garud and Karnøe (2003) summarise the two approaches by arguing that TDE is not just about the discovery of pre-existing options or speculations on the future (Shane, 2000) but also involves the creation of new options through recombination and transformation of existing resources (Garud, Kumaraswamy and Nayyar, 1998; Venkataraman, 2019).

What is common for the different definitions of TDE, is that technological innovations occur before market opportunity identification. Therefore, in order to distinguish between TDE and market-driven entrepreneurship, the definition in this thesis builds upon the description given by Habtay (2012):

Technology-driven entrepreneurship occurs where R&D experimentation and scientific breakthroughs precede market opportunity analysis and the development of a business model.

2.3. Market-driven entrepreneurship

In contrast to TDE, *market-driven entrepreneurship* (MDE) or *market-pull entrepreneurship* is characterised by market demand rather than technology breakthroughs. Relatable to a Kirznerian perspective, MDE “begins with customer creating demand pressure, permitting the identification of new market opportunities as the bases for the innovation that precedes a firm’s likely investment in product or service development activities” (Chaston, 2017, p. 9). Thus, the customer value proposition may evolve over time as the firm gains greater understanding of potential customer needs (McGrath, 2010). The main difference between MDE and TDE is considered to be linked to the originating incentive which prompts development activity, either being a recognition of potential customer needs or scientific/technological knowledge (Chaston, 2017). MDE might encompass complex technology and product development demanding

processes and TDE might be highly adaptive to customer needs and opportunity orientation while conducting product development accordingly (Zahra and Bogner, 2000; Farrington, Henson and Crews, 2012; Pousttchi and Hufenbach, 2014). The difference lies in if technology breakthrough or market information was the outset of a new entrepreneurial venture (Grégoire and Shepherd, 2012; Chaston, 2017).

The definition of MDE in this thesis is derived from Souder (1989), Habtay (2012), and Chaston (2017):

Market-driven entrepreneurship begins with customer creating demand pressure, thus market opportunities precedes a firm's likely investment in R&D.

2.4. Startup definition

Prior to the 1980s, in the context of entrepreneurship and business management, 'startup' was mainly used to describe the early stage of any firm's activity in general (Ray *et al.*, 1974; Seley, 1981). By the 1980s, scholars and practitioners were using the term more specifically referring to a particular kind of work (Cockayne, 2019), mostly related to fast growing semiconductor firms in Silicon Valley (Schoenberger, 1986; Angel, 1989).

Differentiating the term *startup* and its meaning to the more broadly defined term *entrepreneurship* (as described in previous sections) is regarded to be relevant in this context. While entrepreneurship encompasses certain behaviour (Carroll and Mosakowski, 1987; Shane and Venkataraman, 2000) which for example could include entrepreneurial action in large corporations, the empirics in this study is limited towards the study of startups.

In previous literature, mostly three definitional criteria of startups have been used (Luger and Koo, 2005): "new", "active" and "independent". *New* relates to "the creation of an entirely new enterprise which did not formerly exist as an organisation" (Keeble and Norcliffe, 1977). *Active* suggests that the firm should engage in the trading of goods or services (Hadden, 1977; Scott, 1980). Finally, the *Independent* criteria takes into account the lack of any parent organisation (Johnson and Cathcart, 1979), meaning that the firm shouldn't be seen as a branch of an existing business (Mason, 1983).

In theory, the criteria listed above could apply to small business owners as well. Due to the purpose of this study, a more clear definition would need to be established. Carland et al. (1984) states that “although there is an overlap between entrepreneurial firms and small business firms, they are different entities”. They further propose a conceptual distinction between the two types of entities. While a small business venture is regarded as any business that is independently owned and operated but does not engage in innovative practices, an entrepreneurial venture is one that is characterised by innovative strategic practices with the principal goals of profitability and growth. Carland et al. (1984) propose that startups use three key processes. First, by *claiming* a nascent market, preferably by enacting an ambiguous field of opportunities and striving to become an established leader in it. Second, entrepreneurs *demarcate* the market by shaping the surrounding industry structure. By co-opting with established players in nearby markets (Welsh and White, 1981) and specifying the perimeter of the firm they can establish their own well-defined defensible perimeter. Third, entrepreneurs attempt to *control* the market by changing the scope of the market. This ties into the first process, in the way the firm tries to reinforce a dominant position. Relatable to Blue Ocean Strategy (Kim and Mauborgne, 2004), this includes structuring the market in their favor and matching new offerings with unmet needs while eliminating or reducing functions with high competition.

Recently, practitioners advocating a learning-by-doing approach of entrepreneurship – most commonly categorised as Lean Startup (Ries, 2011; Blank, 2013) – mean that startups differ from established companies due to the presence of uncertainty. While established businesses are more used to adapting “big business” tools, creating plans and then executing on those plans, startups rather operate in “search” mode seeking a repeatable and profitable business model (Blank and Dorf, 2012). Simply put, Blank and Dorf (2012) argue that established companies *execute* known business models, while startups need to operate in a *search* mode as they test and prove initial hypotheses.

In order to distinguish *entrepreneurial behaviour*, *new ventures* and *startups*, the definition hereby used for a startup is:

A new, active and independent organisation in search of a scalable, repeatable and profitable business model. Startups pursue to match unmet needs by providing innovative

products/services or using new business models in order to create a unique competitive position.

2.5. Startup stages

A startup is no fixed state, but rather undergoes a quite substantial change throughout the entrepreneurial development process. As described in 1.1. Research purpose, this study focuses on the early stages of the entrepreneurial process.

Within literature, multiple descriptions and models of business life cycle stages or growth stages can be found. (Penrose, 1959; Chandler, 1962; Kimberly, 1979; Kazanjian and Drazin, 1990; Baron and Shane, 2005; Demil and Lecocq, 2010; Levie and Lichtenstein, 2010) Even though most studies examine business stages in general and not only startups, the increased holistic understanding of venture development and growth impact the apprehension of startup stages. Hanks et al. (1994) present a comparison of ten life-cycle models – e.g. (Churchill and Lewis, 1983; Quinn and Cameron, 1983; Miller and Friesen, 1984; Scott and Bruce, 1987; Kazanjian, 1988) – grouping them into 5 distinctive phases: Start-up Stage, Expansion Stage, Maturity Stage, Diversification Stage and Decline. When comparing the Start-Up Stage to the Expansion Stage, a number of distinctions can be made across 7 dimensions (Hanks *et al.*, 1994). Those characteristics are summarised in the table below.

<i>Dimension</i>	Start-Up Stage	Expansion Stage
<i>Age</i>	Young	Young
<i>Size</i>	Small	Small
<i>Growth Rate</i>	Inconsistent	Rapid positive
<i>Structural Form</i>	Undifferentiated, Simple	Departmentalised, Functional
<i>Formalisation</i>	Very informal, personal, flexible; Few policies	Formal systems emerging, enforcement is lax
<i>Centralisation</i>	Highly centralised in founder	Centralised; Limited delegation
<i>Business Tasks</i>	Identify niche; Obtain resources; Build prototype	Volume production & distribution; Set up operating systems

Table 1, Life-Cycle Stage Characteristics, based on Hanks et al. (1994).

Regardless of the adherence to different entrepreneurial methods a common theme can be identified in literature. Namely that most startups transition from a stage of more uncertainty and unproven hypotheses, towards a stage where hypotheses have been proven and the circumstances are more predictable (O'Farrell and Hitchens, 1988; Schoonhoven and Romanelli, 2001; Bhidé, 2003).

Narrowing down on the startup life cycle, Blank and Dorf (2012) introduce the Customer Development model (depicted in Figure 1) describing the phases of an early stage startup. *Customer Discovery* involves formulating a set of business hypotheses and testing those by engaging with potential customers. It also includes verifying customer needs by testing hypotheses through minimal viable products (MVP) and learning from customer feedback. Eric Ries (2011) defines MVP as “a version of a new product, which allows a team to collect the maximum amount of validated learning about customers with the least effort”. By offering customers a minimal product, observation of actual behaviours can be examined which according to lean principles is more reliable than asking people what they would do. The MVPs can be in many forms (Ries, 2011). A Wizard of Oz MVP replaces from the customer side's apparent automated service, with manual work behind the scenes. A Landing Page MVP is used to describe the product on a webpage and collect data about customer behaviour before the product in itself has been developed.

Once *Discovery* is completed, *Customer Validation* is performed by testing the ability to scale. This usually involves validating hypotheses such as pricing, customer acquisition and channel activities. The most common validation activity is through sales, which might be performed without having the product ready that is being sold. *Customer Creation* occurs when customer validation has been proven and when the company is ready to step on the gas and spend time and/or money to scale. The last step is *Company Building*, where a startup has found (and proven) a scalable and repeatable business model. Instead of focusing on “search”, more formal activities – such as sales, marketing and business development along with formalisation efforts such as building departments, hiring VPs and establishing more formalised structures and processes – are carried out. For the context of this study, the focus will lie on the “search” stages rather than the “execute” stages (Figure 1).

Figure 1, Customer Development Process, based on Blank and Dorf (2012, p. 23).

Within prescriptive/non-academic literature, a similar approach to the Customer Development Model is commonly described (McGough, 2016; McGowan, 2017; *Startup Development Phases*, 2018; Riani, 2019). The early stage of a startup in general (not specifically linked to technology-driven startups) is characterised by; *Ideation*, finding a problem, target market and/or product idea; *Concepting*, defining a problem/solution fit, verifying needs and committing to the venture; *Validating*, iterating on a MVP, validating willingness to pay, reaching product-market fit (PMF). The later stages (after having reached PMF) typically include scaling and establishing more effective and professional organisational structures, which lies beyond the scope of this study.

2.6. Entrepreneurial processes

The notion of uncertainty linked to entrepreneurship is far from new. In 1776, Adam Smith (1776) reasoned around the quality of information being used, not necessarily relating it to probability or risk (Brady, 2015). The most notable rejection of this view was formulated by the founder of modern utilitarianism, Jeremy Bentham (1787), who claimed that all probabilities and risks can be calculated in the economics profession, therefore reaching the conclusion that there is no such thing as uncertainty within the business field. Knight (1921) later applied the concept of uncertainty to entrepreneurial contexts, arguing for the entrepreneur's role of exploiting

market opportunities in an ever-changing world with imperfect knowledge of future events. According to Knight (1921), uncertainty is tied to situations where we cannot know all the information to accurately set odds in the first place (Dizikes, 2010). In other words, risk and uncertainty are clearly separated.

As described in Appended study 2: “The issue of decision-making under uncertainty has been thoroughly studied by scholars. Some have proposed rational decision models to manage risk (MacCrimmon, Wehrung and Stanbury, 1986; Focardi and Jonas, 1998; Shapira, 2002) while others have through empirical investigations tried to explain in what way decisions are made in face of uncertainty (Einhorn and Hogarth, 1981; Taylor, 1984; Kahneman and Tversky, 1990).”

Several prescriptive attempts on how to deal with uncertainty have been made by both practitioners and scholars (McGrath and MacMillan, 2000; Sarasvathy, 2001; Baker and Nelson, 2005; Ries, 2011; Blank and Dorf, 2012). Blank (2005) and Ries (2011) – followed by practitioners such as Alvares (2014), Maurya (2012) and Kromer (2019) – prescribe processes of validating critical venture assumptions early in the venture development. By adapting close interactions with real customers as well as testing assumptions with MVPs uncertainty is proclaimed to be reduced.

The Lean Startup and Customer Development, is to a large extent an opposition of traditional business planning processes (Ries, 2011; Blank, 2013). Steinhoff (Steinhoff, 1970) broadly defines business planning as the process of “ascertaining a series of potential courses to be taken by the firm, determining the firm’s position as a result of each potential course, comparing and weighing this position for all actions and, on the basis of the evaluation, selecting the course of action to be followed”. One of the main criticisms of business planning is the assumed existence of a market allowing for planning processes to be established beforehand even though entrepreneurial environments are inherently uncertain (Sarasvathy, 2001; Chwolka and Raith, 2012). Sarasvathy (2001) introduce the concept of effectuation, proposing a number of heuristics including; starting the process with who you are and what you know; embrace the surprise factor and leverage it to your advantage; reduce uncertainty through commitments with early partners;

and focusing on activities within your control rather than attempting to predict the unknown future.

3

Methodology

The following chapter includes a description of overall research methodology, data collection, data analysis and methodology limitations.

3.1. Research methodology

In order to qualitatively discuss empirical data and reach novel observations of benefit for the research purpose, an inductive approach was used (Goddard and Melville, 2004; Bryman and Bell, 2015).

With regards to the research design, the study included:

- (1) a brief literature review and defining of core concepts;
- (2) collection of possible interviewees consisting of Swedish ventures;
- (3) interviewee-screening of tech-driven ventures based on concluded definition in step 1;
- (4) performed interviews with suitable interviewees;
- (5) analysis/discussion of the results in order to answer the proposed research questions.

3.2. Data collection

The data collection was initiated through a collection of companies in the current- and alumni-portfolios of Chalmers Ventures (CV) and Linköping Entrepreneurship and Development (LEAD). A screening process was performed in order to distinguish companies regarded to be technology-driven. This was done by going through the company-portfolios on CV and LEAD webpage where all active and previously active companies were listed. All companies descriptions were read through as well as the company information found on each respective homepage. Based on the gathered information, each company was evaluated as regards to if they

fitted the description of technology based entrepreneurship: *Technology-driven entrepreneurship occurs where R&D experimentation and scientific breakthroughs precede market opportunity analysis and the development of a business model.* (Habtay, 2012). To ensure that the right categorisation had been made, background questions regarding how the business started were asked in the beginning of each interview.

32 companies were approached through LinkedIn-messages, e-mail or phone calls out of which 18 company representatives accepted an interview. Two of the interviews were later discarded from the findings due to the fact that the venture was clearly market-driven or the interviewee was not aware of the venture development activities performed during the early startup stages. This resulted in 16 interviews that formed the main basis of empirical findings in the study (see Table 2). All interviewees except I15 were surrogate entrepreneurs (Lundqvist, 2014), commercialising already existing technology results or ideas.

ID	Founding year	Market segment	Technology	Affiliation
I1	2014	Industrial IOT	Vibration energy harvesting in a small device that can power IOT devices, without the need for cables or batteries	CV
I2	2018	Water filtering	Cleans water from mercury with filter technology	CV
I3	2019	Electric power	AI based tool for minimising disruption in the energy grid	CV
I4	2020	Medtech	Single-cell analysis and manipulation with the use of optics and microfluidics	CV
I5	2017	Glass coatings	A thin-fill of glass for coatings of e.g. plastics too improve UV/scratch resistance	LEAD
I6	2016	Displays	Ultra low-power displays for IOT devices	CV
I7	2014	Algae	Grow algae that silica can be extracted from, both cleans water and produces a sustainable material	CV
I8	2019	Medtech	A device that produces astatine particles that can be used in cancer treatment	CV
I9	2011	Medtech	Nanotechnology for surface gradients for cancer diagnostics	CV
I10	2016	IOT	Energy harvesting from light with carbon based printed	LEAD

			solar panels	
I11	2007	Energy	Energy harvesting from tide with an underwater turbine “plane”	CV
I12	2015	Medtech	Medical treatment for chronic back pain	CV
I13	2017	Medtech	Very early stage cancer diagnostics	CV
I14	2015	Data	Auto-tagging of text solution with the use of AI and machine learning	LEAD
I15	2019	Water filtering	Natural water purification with the help of proteins	CV
I16	2020	Textile	Colouring of clothing that can then be un coloured without the use of harmful chemicals	CV

Table 2, information about the interviewees

The interviews were semi structured with an overarching aim of asking open, non-leading questions and a high extent of follow-up questions (see Appendix 1). Both due to the ongoing Corona-pandemic and geographical limitations, the interviews were held as video calls. During the interview, one person had the main responsibility of asking questions and keeping the conversation going while one person took notes and asked follow-up questions whenever necessary. Transcriptions and notes were finalised directly after the interviews. After the interview the interviewers discussed their findings and thoughts from the interview to be able to create a clear picture that both agreed upon.

Test interviews were performed with two startup founders that had not been selected to be included in the data set. This was to see if the questions were understandable and for the interviewers to practice. They also gave the insight that the 30 minute booked interviews would be very short if the interviewee had long answers. The test interview also gave the interviewers a chance to review some of the questions before starting the interview process.

3.3. Data analysis

When all interviews had been performed, the interview transcriptions and written reflection following each interview were discussed on a holistic level in order to recognise qualitative insights about entrepreneurial processes used. A summary of all interviewees answers with

regard to each set of questions was then put into spreadsheet format. Patterns were identified and key contributions to address the research purpose were highlighted. In order to distinguish between RQ1 and RQ2, all findings linked to processes entrepreneurs *followed* and *recommended to follow* during the first two years, were put into separate categories. Furthermore, the *frequency of mentions* and *emphasis of importance* were noted for answers to each question. Lastly, main topics contributing to answering the research purpose were established which formed the headings in 4. Findings and 5. Discussion.

With regards to RQ3, the findings were quantified based on all mentions of entrepreneurial models. In order to derive qualitative insights, interviewees perceived importance of each particular model was noted. Furthermore, the extent to which the model had been used and in what way it had been applied to the startup, was documented. Some of the interviewees mentioned several models they had heard of but this did not mean that they had applied them to their startup.

3.4. Methodological limitations

One apparent limitation of the study, which also impacts its framing and generalisability, is due to the fact that empirical data was based on two startup hubs with a possible homogeneous context. At both CV and LEAD, certain practices might be emphasised by business coaches, entrepreneurial actors and startups in the same area. At CV, many of the interviewees had studied at CSE, which might cause a preference towards methods taught at that education as well as a pre-existing knowledge of methodologies mentioned in the study. This circumstance, however, is also regarded as an opportunity because of the possibility for interviewees to reason around what practices have worked well for them and/or they recommend for future entrepreneurs with similar circumstances.

All examined startups have a range of how technology-driven they are, therefore placing them all in one category in the first screening is a generalisation (see 5.5. Limitations).

Although the interviewees were framed to be non-leading, by stating the purpose of the study and asking certain questions, a bias might have been introduced in the study. For example,

follow-up questions regarding what models or frameworks were used for need identification, leads the interviewee into providing answers to a type of process they might not have followed.

By combining the interview study with data-collection through surveys, a less subjective interpretation of findings might have been achieved. However, this also introduces disadvantages such as dishonest answers for close-ended questions about following certain methods and less elaborate answers to open-ended questions about processes followed or recommended.

4

Findings

This chapter displays the findings from the semi-structured interviews based on four main topics contributing to relevant findings with regards to the chosen research purpose: Finding market pull; Sell first, build later; Use of networks; and Mentions of used models.

4.1. Finding market pull

Many interviewees stated that the main set of activities performed after having become familiar with the core technology behind the venture, was related to finding market pull. Commonly, verification activities were performed in interaction with potential stakeholders to gain more domain-specific knowledge and insights about needs.

Ventures with very early technologies, that are still in the research phase, claimed to have a very hard time finding market pull. According to those interviewees, a lack of technical attributes which could be clearly linked to adjacent utilities, posed a major obstacle.

Several of the interviewees put forward the idea that it is important to look away from what the technology can do at the get go and instead understand the market needs. This means that there might be of importance to perform a technology pivot, meaning that it can either be exchanged for a totally different solution or that the preliminary technology gets reshaped to solve the identified problem. To conclude the recommendation is to identify the market need, to then be able to fit your solution to that need.

The findings support that choosing market segment and finding market pull is highly related. A majority of the ventures claimed to haven choosen target market based on where they gained market pull.

Several interviewees stated that startups should explore many potential market segments in the beginning. For technology-driven startups, a recurrent theme was that the solution could be adapted to fit many market segments and applications.

One of the ventures, invited 30 people to an evening workshop where participants were given the main scope and then in groups were assigned the task of thinking about every possible application area they could come up with. The founders had gone through most of the ideas beforehand that arose during the brainstorming. However, they found some new application areas for their technology and in an unbiased way, further strengthened their reasons for continuing evaluating market needs in certain industries.

Multiple interviewees recommended a screening process of all potential markets and application areas in order to reduce the risk of having to pivot later on. The applications which were obviously unviable should be disregarded early on in the process.

According to many interviews, a startup should not pursue too many market segments at the same time, 2-4 is recommended. This is to make sure focus can be kept and to ensure that the product development is performed in a defined direction. With a narrowed focus for the entrepreneur, higher results were suggested. I9, for example, recommended to “get a reasonable understanding and then just go for it. [...] Try more, think less”. Most interviewees performed market verification in only a few market segments (more than one) through customer interactions, market analysis and domain specific desk research.

One recurrent theme was that most interviewees choose a main target market segment based on where they got most customer traction. External input from potential customers that showed high interest in solving particular needs with an adaptation of the venture’s technology, sped up the process of choosing market segments.

Furthermore, market pull sometimes emerged from a totally different market or part of the value chain than the venture was originally pursuing. Due to the publicity and exposure of ventures’ technologies and organisations, other industries than the originally anticipated sometimes expressed interest in their technology. In the case of I7, after gaining exposure from a startup competition, explaining the advantages of using their technology for solar cell development, a company from the skin care sector approached them. The company was highly interested in the

attributes related to eco-friendliness and together with I7, they evaluated the possibility of applying the technology to an industry application completely unforeseen by the venture.

I16 and I4 are still in an early stage and looking for the optimum target market segment to gain traction in. They have until this date investigated several markets simultaneously. Yet, they mention that this has been tricky and are now trying to narrow the scope of markets. They further elaborated that they had not found “enough” market pull yet which is the main reason why they have not chosen a main target segment.

Several ventures had decided to choose a market with “small scale” products both because of the ease to prototype as well as the redundancy of larger production facilities. I2 stated that they could not go out and clean whole lakes, even though it in theory would be possible with their technology. This led them to start with the smaller scale application of purifying water at dentist clinics. The dentist practitioners had a small but urgent need of filtering high levels of quicksilver in their wastewater, thus serving as a suitable niche to quicker and more efficiently validate a product-market-fit. When looking for a target segment they had started off with ~20 markets but managed to boil it down to three (dentist clinics being one of them) which were possible to focus on simultaneously.

4.2. Sell first, build later

A topic that arose in the first two interviews and that was asked as a follow-up question in every following interview was if it was suitable for early-stage startups to sell their product before it was developed into a deliverable product. In order to draw quantitative insights, this approach is summarised as a Sell First Build Later approach (SFBL). As outlined in 5.2. Sell first, build later there are both similarities and differences of SFBL compared to MVP. This section will highlight main findings when it comes to the interviewees statements relating to the question “is sell first, build later an appropriate philosophy adhering to?”.

Table 3 summarises if the interviewee actively followed a SFBL-approach and if they recommended such an approach in the context of their venture.

ID	Medtech	Followed	Recommend
I1 I16		Yes	Yes
I2		In part	Yes
I3		In part	Yes
I4	Yes	No	Yes
I5		Yes*	Yes
I6		Yes*	Yes
I7		In part*	Yes**
I8	Yes	No	In part
I9	Yes	In part	Yes
I10		Missing data	Missing data
I11		In part	In part
I12	Yes	In part	No
I13	Yes	No	No
I14		No	Missing data
I15		No	No
I16		No**	In part

* after a while ** with reservation

Table 3, categorisation of each interviewee's answers relating to SFBL.

As shown in Table Table 4, 78% of the ventures recommended to in part or fully follow a SFBL-approach. While 20% stated that they followed a SFBL-approach in their ventures, 57% recommended following a SFBL-approach in the context their ventures existed in.

	Yes	In part	No
All, do	20%	40%	40%
All, should do	57%	21%	21%
Medtech, do	0%	40%	60%
Medtech, should do	40%	20%	40%
Not medtech, do	30%	40%	30%
Not medtech, should do	67%	22%	11%

Table 4, summary of SFBL, grouped between all, medtech and non-medtech ventures.

The only venture that clearly expressed that they followed a SFBL-approach from the beginning was I1. At an early stage they actively sold paid projects for which they did not yet have any prototype or technology ready. The first larger project they entered into was never finished due to mishappenings on the customer's side. I1 stated that for them, it was a great result anyways. They got validation of the customer's willingness to pay, they were able to understand the requirements and processes in that industry and got to build a more finished product according to customer needs.

I1 also recommended that ventures should charge the upcoming final product prize in those SFBL-cases. The venture will most likely go with a large loss due to the time it takes to build the technology used in the project. However, validating willingness to pay is one of the most important tasks according to I1.

Others, such as I2 and I9 stressed that paid pilot projects are important. Most companies are willing to enter pilot projects or get free samples if they have nothing to lose. That however, does not validate any interest from their side. I9 also argued that even if the pilot is paid, an LOI for buying the actual product is important. That the reason why you enter a paid pilot is ultimately to gain validation of the willingness to pay for your future business model, which might not be in project form such as a pilot project is. I11 also argued that releasing a bankable product quickly is much more valuable than releasing a "perfect" product later.

I15 and I16 partly validated customer interest by entering pilot projects where customers did not pay in monetary terms but rather by spending time and resources.

Some interviewees followed a certain approach but answered that they would have done it differently if they were to turn back time. I2, I3, I4, I7 and I9 worked quite heavily with customer interaction and product development, but did not focus on selling something unfinished early which they later regretted. Most interviewees mentioned that most customers wanted a finished product and that even getting signed LOIs is hard before you have that. I4 specifically mentioned a catch-22 situation, where they needed money and validation to build the product customers wanted but that the customers wanted to see a semi-finished product before they were willing to enter joint projects or make orders.

I3, I7 and I8 worked mostly in joint research projects in the early stages and could in that way get closer to a product they could charge for.

I5, I6 and I7 started in a technology-focused way but pivoted to a more SFBL-approach after a while. I5 focused on their own technology and tried finding customers and needs that matched that. When they switched focus to rather building the things customers had a need for, even if it was not a perfect match to their existing technology, they got more positive progress. I6 realised that the problem-solution fit was not existing for their existing technology and therefore switched to a completely new technology for which they could validate market needs. I7 gained exposure for their core technology and therefore got contacted by a market segment they were initially completely unaware of. By building on their initial technology, they could adapt the solution to fit the needs of this market that showed great interest in solving their particular problems.

Both I5 and I7 stressed that you always need to be transparent with your customers about how early your venture is and what it is you sell. You are not trying to fool someone, it's important to build trust. I9 had a partly different approach. According to the interviewee, you have to dare to exaggerate and not tell the full truth to get the sale. That is the main difference between entrepreneurs and technical people in early ventures according to the interviewee. The best products are developed in friction with the customer, that's where you learn the most.

For ventures categorised as being medtech-based, 60% fully or in part recommended a SFBL-approach, while non-medtech ventures recommended or in part recommended SFBL in 89% of the cases (Table 4).

While I4 and I9 recommended SFBL also for medtech, I12 and I13 argued that within medtech, you can not sell something before it's ready. I8 worked closely with customers, sold paid pilot projects and got signed LOIs, but they did not explicitly recommend selling MVPs in early stages.

Lastly, I9 and I11 argued that SFBL might work if you have access to risk capital or other types of external funding. For tech-heavy startups you need a lot of money to develop the technology in accordance to customer needs.

4.3. Use of networks

Regarding RQ1 & RQ2, a majority of the interviewees pointed out how they had used networks in their venture creation process. They also strongly recommended using networks and put emphasis on how important they are. The parts of the network that the interviewees put most emphasis on were; mentors, advisory boards, classmates/alumni, and incubators/coaches. The classmates/alumni category was only mentioned by the interviewees that had studied at CSE.

Mentors are in most cases older, more experienced entrepreneurs that have gone through a similar venture journey before (I12, I1). They are regarded to be helpful even if they don't have experience from the same industry. Many interviewees put emphasis on the importance of having a mentor that you can talk about anything with. If you are new to a particular field, a mentor network can be very helpful just to have somebody you can call and ask stupid questions, which can save very much time and frustration (I12).

According to I1, it can be good to not have a mentor that is too senior. Thereby receiving mentoring from a person having gone through the journey recently and therefore remember more of the details and all the hardship involved.

Many of the interviewed ventures have an advisory board. The advisory board is formed to be a helping hand for the entrepreneurs, with their expertise. Communication was mostly performed on a monthly basis. I1 also stated that it is of value to have more casual relationships with board members. That it is beneficial to have a relationship where you can invite a member over after work and "chat over a pizza and beers".

I11 stated the importance they found in having a mix of competencies in the advisory board, this makes the input from them more nuanced and can cover many sectors. For example they even had a philosopher that helped them a lot with the mental side of starting a new venture.

The majority of the ventures that were interviewed had an education from CSE. They all emphasise the importance of learning from each other in the class, and building a network of people that have gone through the same education. The ventures in the same class are important to benchmark your own venture's progress and discuss possible issues. Ventures in the year

above are important for inspiration and providing guidance as they have been very recently in your shoes.

Building a network during education is helpful for many years to come. The founder of I9 mentioned how he had started two new companies with his desk neighbours from his class. An insight that was brought up was that teams are sometimes swapped around after the education is finished.

Due to the fact that the CSE has existed for more than 20 years, there exist a large number of alumni. I9 and I13 put a large emphasis on the importance of this network and see it as an untapped resource.

Being located close to other startups in an incubator and shared office area is advantageous from a social view (I3). Many of the CSE alumni mentioned that they had been sitting in CV's office spaces which was regarded to be a great setup due to the relationship they could build with the business coaches and the close help they could receive in the early stage.

The ventures originating from LEAD incubator were very happy with the culture and the help they received from the whole ecosystem. I5 and I14 pointed out that they had HR resources in their incubator that were very helpful. They also brought forward the open nature in their incubator where they could talk to all the business coaches even though they had a particular assigned coach.

A CV-affiliated venture mentioned that they did not find the assigned business coaches to be a good match or helpful for the venture, which led to the business developers terminating the coaching service. It was the lack of the coaches startup experience and bad coaching methods which formed their decision to do so.

Many interviewees recommended that new venture teams should focus efforts on establishing a good network. Included in the network there should be mentors, other ventures (in the same stage and further forward), experts in the field and in some cases business coaches.

I11 pointed out how new ventures should not be shy when reaching out to people, and how it is easy to reach out to people and get a mentor. I12 thought that you should spend time on finding a

really good mentor that you like, because his relationship with his mentor had been extremely helpful.

Many ventures recommended that you should work hard on being very nice and likeable towards the people you interact with, as it will increase the engagement and the number of people rooting for your success. This can lead to them paying for pilot projects and recommending you to other potential customers in similar roles.

Students in CSE, or people that have studied there recently, recommended taking advantage of the huge alumni network that has been created over the years. I13 mentioned that a hugely untapped source for knowledge and help exists at universities and that people should become better at reaching out to each other.

4.4. Mentions of used models

As further described in 3.2. Data collection, the interviews were conducted in a semi-structured, non-leading way. By asking “Did you follow any particular method, model or literature during the early stages?” and following up by asking what ones they followed and in what way, both a quantitative and qualitative understanding of usage of models could be gathered. Worth noting, is that those findings are not necessarily related to what methods entrepreneurs adhered to.

Out of 16 interviews, only 2 ventures (I12 and I16) answered that they did not knowingly adhere to any particular method, model or literature in their early stage venture development. The other 14 interviewees mentioned at least one model which was used in their early-stage venture development. On average, every venture mentioned 2.25 models.

Figure 2, number of interviewees (x-axis) mentioning models (y-axis) used in their ventures.

6 interviewees specifically mentioned Lean Startup as a model they, at least in parts, followed. Some had read the Lean Startup (Ries, 2011), others referred to parts of the Lean Startup methodology, especially relating to concepts such as MVP.

Startup Owner's Manual (Blank and Dorf, 2012) was mentioned by 5 ventures. I4 and I2 both followed the general orientation prescribed in the literature and used certain frameworks and resources such as the Exit criteria or the Checklist at the end of every chapter (Blank and Dorf, 2012).

The Mom Test (Fitzpatrick, 2013) was mentioned 4 times as a resource that had been of help in the early venture development stage. A majority of those interviewees claimed to remember the core concepts of the book which guided their customer interactions, rather than using the literature as a template for their performed activities.

5

Discussion

The following chapter brings forward a discussion of main findings. Limitations will be brought up and future directions will be suggested.

5.1. Finding market pull

From reviewing the findings we can conclude that the most important processes in early-stage venture development were identifying market pull and choosing market segments. Due to the two processes being highly intertwined, the findings and discussion regarding those processes are combined in 4.1. Finding market pull and this section, respectively.

As outlined in 1. Introduction, there existed a gap in research regarding the applicability of lean startup principles for technology-driven ventures. The findings from the study supports the view that practitioner-based processes similar to The Lean Startup (Ries, 2011) and Customer Development (Blank and Dorf, 2012) to a large extent guides the activities and strategies technology-driven startups recommend at early venture development stages. One of the most common themes from the interviews included statements supporting the importance of establishing market pull: close and early contact with potential customers; gaining market validation by entering pilot projects, signing letter-of-intents, or pre-orders for unfinished products; and performing business model verification tests with customers before or during product development.

Nonetheless, this study was framed to only study technology-driven startups, which according to our definition entails R&D results and scientific breakthroughs preceding market opportunity analysis. Many of the entrepreneurs interviewed had been matched with research spin-off technologies. When incorporating and aiming to commercialise the research, the first step often

included getting a firm understanding about the core technology and what possible functions, performances and utilities could be linked to it. From our findings, only one interviewee mentioned using a Techno-Economic Analysis (Granstrand, 2001; Lindmark, 2002) for mapping those technological factors with market opportunities. This suggests that either the interviewees familiar with the concepts of similar models followed the core principles without recognition of where those learnings originated from or the interviewees inherently followed similar processes due to cognitive derivability or logical reasoning of their convenience.

A majority of those technology-driven startups, recommended to as quickly as possible evaluate market needs instead of lingering in understanding technological functions and capabilities. Even though it took a long time for some startups to find suitable product-market-fit, almost all (except from medtech-companies), stated that they recommended searching for market pull earlier than they had.

Relating to the theory of effectuation, the findings support at least parts of heuristics described by Sarasvathy (2001). A majority of the interviewees recommended not focusing too much on what problems or needs could be solved with the current technology, rather keeping their eyes open for unforeseen opportunities and non-obvious market needs. Thereby, adhering to the effectuation principle of embracing the surprise factor in order to leverage contingencies. By definition, the technology-driven startups start with their means in the form of scientific results or technological innovations. Still, the findings show that entrepreneurs in tech-driven startups to a lesser extent follow the *Bird in hand* principle of “start with what you have” (Sarasvathy, 2001). Rather, tech-driven entrepreneurs actively seek market pull indications although inconsistent with current knowledge-base or solutions. Existing traits, abilities, attributes and knowledge are mostly neglected in favor of previously unknown indications from the market that leads entrepreneurs to create what the market demands. Those findings to a certain extent help fill the research gap proposed by Agogué et al. (2015) with regards to understanding the effectual or causal processes used by experienced technology entrepreneurs. Our findings support that technology-driven entrepreneurs except, from the Bird in hand principle, mostly adhere to effectual reasoning by allowing contingencies to trigger imaginary rethinking and not assuming pre-determined ends.

The consecutive steps and/or strategies aligning with a market pull approach was not thoroughly investigated in this report. However, according to interviews, processes such as: sell-first-build-later; early customer interaction with viable target market segments; input from external networks and mentors; and to some extent following models (logic and/or tools); were most commonly mentioned.

In contrast to what Chaston (2017) argues regarding technology-driven entrepreneurs and how they “postpone any consideration of the commercial viability”, our findings support the fact that technology-driven entrepreneurs deeply contemplate market conditions and customer needs before diving too deep into product development. One reason for this fact might be that TD-entrepreneurs do not perceive themselves to be technology-driven due to a majority having been surrogate entrepreneurs. Another explanation might be found as a consequence of the previous knowledge and education the interviewees have received from Chalmers School of Entrepreneurship, Chalmers Ventures or LEAD Business Incubator.

Many of the processes mentioned by entrepreneurs during the early-stages of venture development, were related to choosing a suitable target market worth pursuing. This process is likely to be more frequent in TDE than MDE, due to the origin of a market-driven venture often being specific demands from a particular market segment.

For some of the tech-driven ventures, the choice of market was a natural consequence of indicated market pull. Others had a harder time in deciding where to focus their resources and energy when pursuing certain markets. Several ventures had pursued many market segments in parallel for a long time which according to externally described processes is not ideal (Moore, 2006; Blank and Dorf, 2012). When reflecting upon what they should have done differently, those ventures often advocated the process of deep diving into one potential market and being open for pivoting quickly if the market did not prove viable (Ries, 2011; Blank and Dorf, 2012).

Ideally every segment should be explored to a large extent. However, due to startups scarce resources and time being of importance they have to focus on one at a time. There are also perks with choosing a niche segment such as competitive advantage (Moore, 2006) and more tailor-made customer solutions.

Another process recommended by startups such as I7 is to produce publicity for the venture through media coverage, competitions, etc. That way, customers in market segments the venture initially are unaware of might express their interest in solving hidden problems based on the venture's technology. Thus finding a suitable niche segment without having to scope out markets, investigating them, contacting stakeholders etc (see Figure 3).

By reviewing the findings, four main stages could be identified when it comes to the process of choosing market segments. Those are summarised in Figure 3. It should be noted that the figure is a simplification of stages which have been mentioned and recommended by many tech-driven entrepreneurs. However, the summarising figure should not be interpreted as a prescriptive theory to be followed by entrepreneurs. We encourage further research in order to study the applicability of market-segment strategy in the early phases of technology-driven ventures. Nonetheless, the summary is considered to be a contribution when it comes to the understanding of processes most commonly used by technology-driven entrepreneurs.

Figure 3, funnel for choosing market

1. A majority of interviewees stated that their technology was applicable to multiple market segments. This is seen as a logical consequence derived from the scope of studying technology-driven ventures. In contrast to market-driven entrepreneurship, where recognition of market opportunities precede R&D, technology-driven ventures rarely knew what market their technology was adequately suited for.

2. Our findings suggest that most technology-driven entrepreneurs performed an early screening of viable markets, based on technological capabilities and possible utilities derived from those capabilities.
3. Most technology-driven entrepreneurs recommend not pursuing too many market segments at the same time. Different ways of evaluating viable markets were mentioned, including early indication of market pull, desk research and on a basis of internal capabilities. However, a detailed investigation of how the scoping process was performed lies outside the bounds of this study.
4. When having narrowed down the scope, most commonly customer-verification activities were performed in close contact with potential customers and stakeholders in the pursued markets. The expressed goal was to gather as concrete validation of customer demand, product-market-fit and willingness to pay, in order to determine a main target segment for a go-to-market-strategy.

Worth mentioning, is that market pull sometimes emerged at any of the four described stages. In the cases where this occurrence was mentioned by interviewees, everyone recommended to put effort on that particular market in favor of markets without clearly expressed needs from potential customers.

5.2. Sell first, build later

From the first two interviews, a process of “sell first, build later” emerged, leading to us asking questions relating to if “sell first, build later is an appropriate philosophy adhering to” in consecutive interviews. Being strongly linked to finding market pull (see previous section) and Lean Startup like methodologies; the activities related to SFBL support the notion that many tech-driven entrepreneurs follow and recommend the process of gaining market traction before focusing on product development.

Comparing SFBL to MVP (Ries, 2011; Brikman, 2015, 2016; Lenarduzzi and Taibi, 2016), several similarities and differences can be discussed. MVP is defined by Eric Ries (2011) as “a version of a new product, which allows a team to collect the maximum amount of validated

learning about customers with the least effort”. Similar to the findings of the SFBL-approach, MVPs are used to validate critical business assumptions directly with potential customers.

Nonetheless, our findings suggest that processes that are different from MVP-testing are commonly mentioned by tech-driven entrepreneurs.

- While MVPs should be the foundation of a product, “a product which has just those features and no more that allows you to ship a product that early adopters see [...] and start to give you feedback on” (Ries, 2011), SFBL is used to make customers validate their interest by paying for the product you later will build.
- Common MVPs are “wizard of oz” or “landing-page-tests” (see 2.5. Startup stages). Several interviewees state that the process they recommend is not about “tricking” the customer, rather being transparent with limitations and reservations. Up-front payments is one way to do so.
- SFBL does not have to sell a promise of your final product. Instead, it might involve selling joint projects, pilot projects and consultancies in order to both gain monetary means to build the scalable product and gain insights in what the product should entail to meet customer demands.

While only 20% stated that they followed a SFBL-approach, 78% of the ventures fully or in part recommended the process. Even though the findings don’t clearly outline the reasons behind the difference between what the entrepreneurs did and what they recommended, some possible reasons for the discrepancy can be suggested:

Firstly, many of the ventures were the first entrepreneurial ventures the interviewees had founded. Having gone through the process several times, increases the probability of a firm’s survival and success (Plehn-Dujowich, 2010; Lafontaine and Shaw, 2016). Nonetheless, prior research suggests that the main reason for the success of serial entrepreneurs is due to selection on ability, rather than the result of learning by doing (Rocha, Carneiro and Varum, 2015). Still, many of the interviewees pointed out pitfalls and after-the-fact reasoning about non-suitable processes followed. The fact that those entrepreneurs mostly stayed in the same ventures and changed processes in order to become more successful, does not contradict either the argument

of *ability* or *learning-by-doing* being the contributing factor of positive venture development progress.

Secondly, SFBL might not appear intuitive. The perception of entrepreneurship might by common belief be related to “get a great idea, raise money, build it, sell it”. Switching places between *selling* and *building* is not obvious. How could you possibly sell something you don’t have?

Thirdly, tech-driven entrepreneurs might have followed effectuation principles, especially corresponding with the Bird in Hand Principle (Sarasvathy, 2001). Starting with their means, in particular technological results, the entrepreneurs might adhere to existing knowledge and expertise rather than actively seeking unforeseen customer needs. Our findings suggest that tech-driven entrepreneurs do not knowingly follow effectuation principles. A majority of interviewees connected to CSE have become familiar with effectuation principles from their education. The possibility that the logic from this model has stuck is not unlikely.

Lastly, two seasoned interviewed entrepreneurs argued that SFBL might only work if having access to a considerable amount of capital. They argue that you need to show something in order to get signed orders or validated customer traction. This “something” is always related to a cost, and most likely the high-tech contexts, in which many tech-driven ventures exist, require a higher degree of capital injection to cover those costs. One objection to this argument might be that talking to customers, forming letter-of-intents or agreeing on pilot-projects would not be less costly than product development. In the cases where it is possible to sell based on a promise to deliver certain future results, the SFBL-approach does not necessarily require a higher amount of capital.

Another insight based on the findings relates to the pricing of early sales in a venture. Although not thoroughly established within this study, our findings point toward the claim that the more seasoned the entrepreneur is, the more they recommend pricing early products, projects or solutions higher than non-seasoned entrepreneurs do. Establishing a willingness to pay is regarded to be of essence, as that is an important business model hypotheses to validate early on in the venture development. Those entrepreneurs are aware of the fact that the solution might

cost more to bring customers at an early stage compared to later. Therefore they recommend pricing accordingly to what the anticipated product price will be in the future. Even if the interviewees seldom mentioned Crossing the Chasm theory (Moore, 2006), adhering to a logic of selling to early adopters, who are willing to take risks to stay competitive and are not as sensitive to price, might be one of the reasons why it is important to focus on customers who can pay.

Fig 4, medtech ventures recommending SMBL

Fig 5, non-medtech ventures recommending SMBL

Our findings suggest that one main differentiator when it comes to who recommends a SFBL-approach exists. Entrepreneurs involved in medtech ventures are less likely to recommend selling before building. While 67% of non-medtech ventures recommended SFBL, only 40% did so in medtech ventures (see Fig 5, Fig 4). The main argument for this was that in those contexts, it is not possible to sell something before it is ready. You might work closely with potential customers and try to understand their needs and interest in the proposed solution. However, large product development efforts are considered to be needed in order to get paid in monetary terms for a solution.

5.3. Use of networks

Today's startup models do not put large emphasis on how to use networks (D'Abate, Eddy and Tannenbaum, 2003). Though models such as Lean startup are often used in coaching settings (Mansoori, Karlsson and Lundqvist, 2019). For example in the Lean startup the importance of networks is not brought up (Ries, 2011). However, this is something that the interviewed

entrepreneurs focus on. As well as something they recommend startups to do. Which indicates that it is an important factor in entrepreneurship.

When it comes to using networks the majority of the interviewees mentioned that mentors was the most important external stakeholder they had. The mentors did more than provide guidance, expertise and help with entrepreneurial processes; they also helped the entrepreneurs with soft values such as motivation. This is in accordance with what research into entrepreneurship mentorship is exploring, the author points out the big importance for mentors to newly graduated college students for them to pursue an entrepreneurship career (Deepali, Jain and Chaudhary, 2016). The author even points out that the mentor doesn't have to be from the same industry, but instead it is the notion of entrepreneurship and soft values that are important for the mentee.

Advisory board was brought during several interviews, this typically a collection of people with varied skills that were mainly focused on helping and "advising" the entrepreneurs. In literature the same perception of the importance of advisory boards is brought forward. Lusk & Harrison argue that they can save entrepreneurs, "years of painful and costly mistakes" (McGillicuddy, 2004). Skills that were brought up in the interviewees were typically scientific experts, people with market knowledge and in one case a person with a background in psychology. This is interesting due to the fact that the willingness of involvement in the company even though they did not have equity.

The high number of interviewees that had gone to CSE led to many good insights regarding the network that it gives. A number of these mentioned that it was the most part of the education. This was due to the importance in the second year of sitting together and learning from each other. And after graduating there are many possibilities that open up regarding new ventures. The insight given by alumni that the network should be used more. This is something that is increasing during education, where the ventures get matched up with alumni in the same industry for mentoring and coaching.

Incubators and the coaches that often come in that setting gave insights into the importance of working in a close proximity with other startups in the early-stage. This can be linked to the second year of CSE where the ventures share a co-working space.

The interviewees had mixed experiences regarding coaches, this can be linked to Lundquist's findings regarding applying lean startup in coaching. The article comes to the conclusion that coaches can have a hard time being neutral to hypotheses and data (Mansoori, Karlsson and Lundqvist, 2019). Which leads the coached party with a dilemma in what route to pursue with the venture. An important insight is that it depends a lot between coaches and entrepreneurs, and their willingness to be coached.

The figure Figure 6 is a diagram to represent the findings from the interviews regarding the entrepreneurs network. It's a venture centric model that is displayed, meaning that the parts that are most often contacted and of greatest importance for the entrepreneur are closest to the middle. For example mentors are most used and frequently contacted; they are placed close to the center. This illustration represents the part networks played during the first two years of the venture.

Figure 6, a venture centric model with most frequently contacted stakeholders closest to the center.

5.4. Mentions of used models

In order to draw conclusions about RQ3, each interviewee was asked questions regarding what models were used as well as how they are perceived to bring value. In 4.4. Mentions of used models a quantitative representation of models mentioned are outlined. After reviewing the way

entrepreneurs consider how different models contribute with value, two main categories could be distinguished: *Logic* or *tool*.

Logic models are used by entrepreneurs as a general rationale for orienting venture development activities. By adhering to indefinite advice, general prescriptions or heuristics in those models, entrepreneurs form their own processes which are applicable to their specific entrepreneurial context and prerequisites. Logic is therefore more of a “way of thinking” than “what to think”.

Tools are models used in a less abstract way than logic models. They encompass concrete techniques or specific prescriptions to be carried out by the ventures. Some tools are also used as ways to structure data and map out relations. Instead of being used as an overarching philosophy, tools are to a higher extent used to help entrepreneurs with a distinct issue. Examples include mapping technical capabilities with customer needs, getting a clear overview of the business model, and questions to ask potential customers. Tools therefore outline “how to do” or “what to think”, rather than “way of thinking”.

Our findings support that some models are used as tools in some cases while the same model is utilised as a “way of thinking” in other cases. Those models are categorised as being both *logic and tools*. For example, the checklists in the end of each chapter in Startup Owner’s Manual (Blank and Dorf, 2012) was used “as-is” by some interviewees, at the same time they followed the overarching philosophy of Customer Development outlined in the book.

In Figure 7 the categorisation is visualised and color coded in order to provide better understanding of the following discussion.

Figure 7, models categorised as being used as a logic (blue), a tool (green) or both as a logic and tool (yellow).

The categorisation is similar to an organising framework introduced by Yashsar Mansoori (2017, p. 49). The framework can be used to break down three hierarchical levels represented in entrepreneurial methods. In the three-tier framework, *logic* lies at the highest level of abstraction (thought) while *tactics* are geared toward accomplishing immediate objectives (action). In between logic and tactics, *model* “acts as a bridge between high-level cognitive ideas and low-level practical activities” thereby lying at an intermediate level between logic and tactics (Mansoori, 2017).

Two important differences exist between the three-tier framework (Mansoori, 2017) and the differentiation between logic and tools made in this thesis. Firstly, while the three-tier framework is used to organise the building blocks of entrepreneurial *methods*, this thesis’ logic-tool-differentiation is used to categorise how *models* are used by entrepreneurs. Thus, it should be noted that the definition of models in this thesis (a set of non-mutually exclusive methods, prescriptions, tactics and frameworks established in both academic and non-academic literature), is very different from Mansoori’s (2017) definition of models (see previous paragraph). This section discusses models used, not methods. Secondly, this thesis’ logic-tool-differentiation is used to differentiate how models are used, thereby following an “either-or” approach. Mansoori’s framework is proposed to explain three layers of the same method. Each method consists of all three layers in the three-tier framework while in this thesis’ logic-tool-differentiation, the models are used as either logic or tool.

By reviewing the interviewees explanations of how the models were used, a categorisation could be made differentiating *logic*, *tool*, and *logic and tool* (see Figure 8).

Figure 8, number of interviewees (x-axis) mentioning models (y-axis) used in their ventures.

Although a majority of the interviewees had a background from entrepreneurship education, on average only 2.25 entrepreneurial models were mentioned per venture. Furthermore, at most 6 ventures mentioned having used a particular model (The Lean Startup). It should be noted that this does not indicate that tech-driven ventures did not follow any of the models. Most of the models consist of prescriptive steps to be followed by startups. Tech-driven ventures might follow those steps more or less according to the models, even without knowing about them. Nonetheless, what can be suggested by analysing those results is that entrepreneurs do not knowingly use models to any higher extent.

While the ventures mentioned models being used as logic 21 times, tools were mentioned only 10 times. This might imply that a general direction and overarching philosophy is of more use for tech-driven entrepreneurs. In the case of Lean Startup and Customer Development for example, a majority answered that they followed the logic of measuring customer demand and testing something early with MVPs. However, most stressed that they did not specifically follow the specific actions described in the literature. Rather, they created their own activities with the logic of the model in the back of their minds. Another interpretation of the findings, is that more people followed a Lean Startup or Customer Development focused approach than stated using

them as models. If this is because they did not remember them by name or if they conducted those processes inherently, remain unsaid.

The interpretation of ventures mentioning Business planning, was that the model was used mainly as a tool. The interviewees remarked that they needed business plans for competitions or investor meetings, indicating that the value was linked to improving legitimacy and/or following institutionalised rules rather than increased performance in the venture (Honig and Karlsson, 2004). Another point being brought up was that in the ever-changing environment of entrepreneurship, a business plan proved to be of low value for the venture in itself, indicating a tendency towards other forms of early-stage venture processes (Blank, 2013).

Surprisingly, many of the tools were mentioned only once. Those included CK-theory, Effectuation, TEVA, NABC and Lean Canvas. This suggests that most entrepreneurs' everyday activities do not entail using external tools or reading up on suggested processes in literature for performing tasks such as business modelling, pitch communication, or market segmentation analysis. The findings seem to indicate that entrepreneurship is a craft, where entrepreneurs learn by doing rather than relying on existing literature.

5.5. Limitations

We acknowledge several limitations of this study impacting the generalisation of our results and following conclusions.

When conducting the interviews we recognised the difficulty for interviewees remembering specific processes they went through many years ago. This might lead to misinterpretation especially when it comes to models being used but also processes adhered to in early-stage venture development. The human mind often romanticizes old memories (Anderson, Bjork and Bjork, 2000). Meaning in our case the interviewees did not explain the process as long and tedious but instead as just another part of the successful journey. We got the impression that they much rather talked about success than hardship.

We chose to not measure venture success in the study, nor use it as a factor when choosing interviewees. Yet we only interviewed successful ventures in that meaning that they still were

active. This can also affect the result because of survivorship bias, for future research the same study but instead interviewing failed startups would be interesting.

An insight that was realized when performing the screening process was that there is a scale between TDE and MDE and it is not two totally different categories. Meaning that the categorisation we make of TDE comes from advanced research, one might have to dig deeper looking at why the researchers research on that topic. Was it to fill a need that they saw in the market? Even though research at universities should not be focused on satisfying market needs.

In our meaning, the semi structured interview format resulted in many good insights and discussion topics of benefit for the thesis as a whole. However, in some interviews the subject was very much into storytelling which led to the time of the interview running out before all questions had been asked and all topics discussed. Luckily some of the interviewees had the possibility to carry on even though the time had run out. Due to the fact that we realised during the practice interview that this could have been a problem we should have rebooked and extended the interviews. Nonetheless there were advantages with booking 30min interviews such as the high conversion rate of people wanting to attend.

Furthermore, the chosen method limited our ability to quantify results in a way that could have resulted in other types of finding. For example, the mentioned models were highly diverse in nature and led to less generalisability of findings and coherent analysis of qualitative findings.

Differences exist with regards to: references to a single book or a collection of similar sources; practitioner-based or scholarly-based; focus on different entrepreneurial activities (such as sales, go-to-market-strategy or business modelling); and level of comprehensiveness.

5.6. Future directions

Many of the topics included in this thesis, as well as some of the discussion points brought up are recommended to be further investigated.

One of the discussions brought up in this thesis concerns ventures with a medtech background, Those ventures seem to recommend different processes than other tech-driven startups, indicating that prescribed processes should differ between those two contexts. The long time to

market and discussion points related to SFBL (see 5.2. Sell first, build later suggests that further research into what processes are used and/or recommended for medtech companies would be valuable for practitioners.

Alumni from CSE did not mention that they used or remembered the methods that they had been taught during their education. Is this because the education is not applicable enough to entrepreneurs' reality? Have they gained knowledge of benefit for their entrepreneurial careers although the specific models taught did not stick? An evaluation of how the processes adhered to by CSE-alumni compared to other entrepreneurs might be of high value for the future design of entrepreneurial education.

A topic that also sparked our curiosity was that the use of mentors was something that was highly recommended by the interviewees. Due to the extensive scope of this topic, it could not be explored to the extent it might prove useful for scholars and practitioners in the field of entrepreneurship. Even though topics related to social capital, use of networks, and entrepreneurial peer-to-peer learning have been subject to much research in the past, we miss specific examination of how early-stage entrepreneurs benefit from what type of mentorship.

6

Conclusions

The purpose of this thesis has been to explore processes followed and/or recommended by early stage technology-driven startups. Following an inductive research approach, empirical data was gathered based on semi-structured interviews with 16 entrepreneurs. The findings suggest that although technology-driven entrepreneurs start their commercialisation processes based on technological results, they recommend the process of finding market pull as quickly and efficiently as possible which also impacts their choice of market segment. Except for medtech-based ventures, technology-driven venture's main goal is to transition into market-driven ventures, focusing on serving untapped market needs and unforeseen opportunities. Comparing our findings with theory of effectuation, our findings suggest that tech-driven entrepreneurs adhere to the principle of embracing the surprise factor in order to leverage contingencies. However, in contrast to the principle of *Bird in hand*, our findings indicate that entrepreneurs adapt processes neglecting "what they have" in favour of previously unknown market demands. This raises the question if the heuristics outlined in the theory of effectuation are better suited for market-driven instead of technology-driven ventures. We encourage further research to shed light on this issue.

Furthermore, our findings suggest that lean principles are followed to a large extent also in technology-driven ventures. Entrepreneurs highlight the importance of establishing market pull by creating close and early contact with potential customers and performing business model verification tests with customers before or during product development. In many cases, they adopt processes similar to MVP-testing. However, our study concludes an important difference with regards to processes used and recommended by technology-driven entrepreneurs. This contribution is summarised as a Sell-first-build-later (SFBL) approach. In contrast to MVP-testing, SFBL involves being transparent with potential customers about current

limitations and focus on sales of joint projects, pilot projects or consultancy services while developing a scalable product that customers are willing to continue paying for.

Our study indicates that technology-driven entrepreneurs put a large emphasis on the importance of personal networks. Those include, but are not limited to: mentors, other entrepreneurs, advisors and alumnis. The importance of personal networks is heavily understated within prescriptive theories of entrepreneurship. Thus, the discrepancy between technology-driven entrepreneurs' perceived importance of personal networks and the existing gap in prescriptive entrepreneurship literature, is a topic of relevance for further research.

By exploring what entrepreneurial models technology-driven entrepreneurs use and/or recommend, as well as how they are utilised, several intriguing discussion points can be made. Two main categories could be distinguished by reviewing how the models are perceived to contribute with value. *Logic* models provide entrepreneurs with a general rationale, being used as a “way of thinking”. *Tools*, on the other hand, are used as concrete techniques or ways to structure data and help entrepreneurs deal with distinct issues or perform certain activities. The findings support that logic models are used to a higher extent than tools by technology-driven entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs don't blindly follow prescriptive tactics outlined in literature. Rather, they have a certain logic in the back of their minds. General mindsets such as validating market demand in close contact with potential customers indicate an inclination towards lean startup principles. Still, lean startup *tools* seem to be more seldomly used by technology-driven entrepreneurs.

This thesis has attempted to advance the understanding around processes used and recommended by (and for) technology-driven entrepreneurs. We argue that this thesis' contributions, at least in part, helps to fill some research gaps proposed by several authors regarding the applicability of lean startup-like processes in technology-driven entrepreneurship.

As subject to further investigation, providing a more nuanced and in-depth picture of what processes are most suitable for ventures in both tech-driven and market-driven contexts is firmly believed to be of great value for future entrepreneurs. Admittedly, a “Lean Startup for TDE” is perhaps too much to hope for.

7

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8

Appendices

In the following chapter appendices related to the thesis are presented.

- Appendix 1: Interview script, page 57
- Appendix 2: Models mentioned per venture, page 59

Appendix 1: Interview script

Introduction and framing of interview.

- *We are studying the second year on Chalmers School of Entrepreneurship and are involved in a venture each as well.*
- *We are performing a Master thesis focused on what startups did during the early phases of their ventures.*

Background

- Tell us about yourself and [your venture]?
 - What educational background do you have?
 - What roles have you had in the venture?
 - Did you have experience of entrepreneurship from before?
 - Have you had any formal education connected to entrepreneurship?
- How did it all start with [your venture]?
 - *Follow-up questions to understand if the venture started as technology- or market-driven.*

If you think back to the first two years of the venture's journey:

- In general, what were the focus of your activities during this time?
 - How did you proceed with regards to:
 - Choice of market or application?
 - Customer need identification?
 - Business modelling?
 - Product development?
 - *Etc. based on the context*
- Did you follow any particular method, model or literature during the early stages of venture development?
 - Follow-up question: Did you follow any method, model or literature related to:
 - Choice of market or application?
 - Customer need identification?
 - Business modelling?
 - Product development?
 - *Etc. based on the context*

- Did you work with mentors and external networks?
 - *If yes:* How did you work with mentors and external networks?
 - *If yes:* What is the importance of mentors and external networks according to you?

Not necessarily related to what the ventures did:

- Would you have done anything differently if you could have gone back in time (without knowing what you know now)?
- What is your general advice on the process at the beginning of entrepreneurial journeys in technical intensive startups?
- What methods, models and/or literature do you recommend for ventures in a context similar to your's?
- Is a “sell-first-build-later”-approach suitable for ventures in your context?
- If you would have created an own methodology for your company, what steps would it exist of?

Outro

- Do you wish to add something more?
- Do you wish to ask us something?
- Do you know any other tech-driven startup that could be interesting for us to talk to?

Appendix 2: Models mentioned per venture

	I1	I2	I3	I4	I5	I6	I7	I8	I9	I10	I11	I12	I13	I14	I15	I16	SUM	
Business planning		■						■					■				3	
Business Model Canvas				■					■					■			3	
CK-theory	■																1	
Crossing the chasm				■			■										2	
Effectuation	■																1	
LEAD Process					■					■				■			3	
Lean Canvas								■									1	
Lean Startup		■	■			■				■			■		■		6	
Mega Deals										■							1	
NABC					■												1	
Solution Selling														■			1	
Startup Owner's Manual		■	■	■						■				■			5	
TEVA	■																1	
The Mom Test		■		■		■									■		4	
TRL-scale											■		■				2	
Zero to One						■											1	
SUM Logic	■	1	2	2	1	2	3	1	0	0	3	0	0	2	2	2	0	21
SUM Tool	■	2	1	0	1	0	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	10
SUM Logic and tool	■	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	5